

ORGANIZATIONAL PEDAGOGICAL PRINCIPLES OF LEADING STUDENTS IN CLASSROOM AND OUTSIDE-SCHOOL ACTIVITIES

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Abstract: The main task of the education sector is to provide our youth with in-depth knowledge in accordance with the international educational standards, to educate them in the spirit of love for the Motherland and loyalty to the ideals of national independence. In this article, we have studied the organizational and pedagogic foundations of leading students in their classroom and extracurricular activities for quality and creative learning.

Key words: Pedagogy, Adult education, Creative process, consciousness, educator, management culture, 9 basic rules

Main part: The term "Pedagogy" refers to how teachers teach in practice and in theory. Pedagogy is shaped by the educational beliefs of the teacher and is the interplay between culture and different teaching methods. Pedagogy is concerned with the study of teaching strategies and how they affect students. . Thoughtful and effective pedagogy is critical to helping students learn more successfully and develop higher-order thinking skills. Online education presents unique challenges and opportunities for educators, and strong pedagogy is necessary to ensure that students learn effectively through online education. This may include using age-appropriate teaching strategies and materials, as well as understanding a child's developmental stages and how they affect learning.

A strong pedagogy in distance education must also consider the needs and learning styles of distance learners. This may include using personalized learning plans and other approaches that allow students to learn at their own pace and in the way that works best for them.

In this article, we explore the learning process and how it can be fostered using evidence-based teaching strategies.

One popular pedagogy for teaching is constructivist pedagogy, which emphasizes the importance of active learning and student engagement in the learning process.

This approach emphasizes the idea that knowledge is constructed by the learner rather than by the teacher.

Constructivist pedagogy encourages students to ask questions, explore ideas, and collaborate with others to build their own understanding of the material. Using this approach, teachers can help students develop critical thinking skills and learn more independently.

A general education school is an educational institution. Its leaders are entrusted with the task of teaching and educating the young generation, managing the process of forming a human personality in the spirit of the ideas of the current era. In society, every economic system and production center is a unit of two systems: the controlled and the controlling system. For example, in the enterprise system, the entire management apparatus of the factory department headed by the director is included in the management system. The internal management system of the school is based on these rules. From this point of view, the internal management system of the school has both the manager (school administration, trade union organizations) and managed systems. For example, in the internal management system of the school, the headmaster, his deputies for educational, educational and economic affairs are part of the managed system.

Managing a school is a creative process and a unique art. This pedagogic process is manifested in the different work methods of school leaders. These methods allow every leader to learn theoretically and practically the current issues of school science, to study the advanced pedagogical experiences in the field of school education, and the opinion of influential people in this field (employees of public education bodies, school teachers and educators) on school management. and requires the study of opinions and the creative use of these opinions and opinions in the process of managing school work. This, in turn, is of great importance in managing school work and further improving the leadership style. Every leader is an educator. He should fully have a sense of high responsibility for educating the pedagogical team. The leader should be able to influence the personality of his subordinates with such a pedagogical culture that, as a result of this influence, consciousness is formed in each member of the team of pedagogues of this school, he has a creative approach to pedagogical work, and actively participates in social life. please The ability of the school director to understand the opinions of his subordinates and representatives of public organizations in the school and quickly draw correct conclusions is important in the proper organization of management work. Educational and economic issues of the school should be discussed by the council, every member of the team of school pedagogues should take the initiative

in implementing the adopted decisions. It is appropriate to evaluate the work of the head in school management, not by the time spent on decision-making, but by taking into account the final result of his activity. The head of the school is responsible for the development of friendly cooperation and mutual assistance in the team of pedagogues. The existence of a good social and psychological environment and situation in the school community depends to a large extent on the relationship between the leader and teachers and educators. It is possible to create a normal pedagogical work situation and correct mutual relations in the team only if there is strong discipline. Strong pedagogical discipline is achieved through the demandingness of the head of the school, the development of criticism and self-criticism, as well as transparency.

Adult education

Pedagogy is also important in adult education. Unlike traditional education, which often focuses on the acquisition of knowledge and skills, adult education typically focuses on helping adults develop new competencies, learn new skills, and acquire knowledge relevant to their current or future career. .

Pedagogy in adult education often focuses on creating a supportive and engaging learning environment that is conducive to meeting the unique needs of adult learners. This may include the use of interactive and experiential learning activities, as well as real-life examples and case studies relevant to learners' experiences and interests. Access to education is also an important consideration, as many adults may have difficulty accessing educational opportunities due to work, family, and other commitments. A strong adult education pedagogy must take these issues into account and strive to make learning as accessible as possible for adult learners.

Conclusion: Organizational pedagogic principles of guiding students in classroom and extracurricular activities will help them learn to master and master in the educational process. These grounds may be:

- ✚ Increase individual approach to ensure students' mastery.
- ✚ To increase the motivation of students to increase their mastery.
- ✚ Development of critical thinking to improve students' mastery.
- ✚ Ensuring physical and mental health of students to improve their learning.
- ✚ Setting goals and objectives to improve students' learning.
- ✚ Using effective means of communication to improve students' learning.
- ✚ Cooperation with the community to improve students' learning.
- ✚ Use of new technologies to improve students' learning.

- ✚ To ensure that students achieve personal development and self-analysis to improve their mastery.

These principles are important in guiding students in their classroom and extracurricular activities, and by implementing them, they can help students develop at a higher level and make appropriate career choices.

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